

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 3.3 Disseminate knowledge
developed by the Networks and TWGs
through external workshop events

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report is an overview of the external workshop events organised by the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat, between November 2022 and June 2025, to disseminate knowledge and recommendations from the Networks and Temporary Working Groups to broader stakeholders.

1.1 Knowledge developed and disseminated by the Networks and temporary working groups

Deliverable 3.3 involves disseminating knowledge developed by the Zero Emission Platform's Networks (now referred to as Committees) and Technical Working Groups (TWGs) through external workshop events. This initiative targets stakeholders across various sectors, including industry professionals, policymakers, researchers, and environmental organisations. The primary goal is to share insights and advancements in carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) technologies that have been discussed and brought forward by the Networks and TWGs. These events are organised periodically and held at various international venues to maximise outreach and impact.

The Networks and TWGs include the Projects Network which acts as forum where CCS and CCU project developers exchange information, discuss enablers and hurdles, good practices, and de-risking on planned and ongoing projects across Europe, and engage with European, regional, national and local policymakers. The Technology Committee (TC) encompasses an assortment of working groups that focus on the technological challenges, opportunities, risks and costs associated with CCS and CCU. The TC includes a Working Group on Carbon Dioxide Removal and a TWG on CO₂ Storage. The Policy and Economics Committee (PEC) gathers stakeholders interested in the development and deployment of CCS and CCU in Europe. The PEC includes a Working Group on Policy and Funding and included a TWG on Transport by Ship. Lastly, the External Relations Committee provides strategic guidance to ZEP's external communications activities, as well as in promoting ZEP's mission and identity across its wide network of stakeholders.

The Networks and corresponding TWGs serve as a knowledge sharing platform for presenting research findings and ensuring that the latest knowledge and best practices are widely disseminated and implemented. Further discussions in these sessions include the intersection of CCS with policy initiatives like the Net Zero Industry Act, safeguarding jobs, and industrial competitiveness in a climate-neutral Europe.

2 ANNEX A: OVERVIEW OF EXTERNAL WORKSHOP EVENTS

Annex A includes an overview of the external workshop events that the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat gave between November 2022 and June 2025 based on work from the Networks and TWGs. Most of these presentations were webinars, focusing on EU policy and market developments of CCS and CCU as well as technological advancements.

Meeting	Date	Attendees	Key ZEP contributions
Webinar: Building a European CO ₂ transport and storage infrastructure	9 March 2023	205	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate discussion between project developers, EU institutions, NGOs, and governments on European CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure.
Net zero within reach	26 April 2023	170	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In collaboration with the CCSA, hosted a conference in Brussels. Facilitate discussion between CCS and CCU industry and technology providers, thought leaders, policymakers, researchers, and civil society to share their insights on net zero technologies.
CCS and the Net Zero Industry Act ZEP knowledge-sharing seminar	13 June 2023	18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide an overview of CCS and CCU technologies and how they can support the EU transition to climate neutrality. Facilitate discussion between NGOs, industrial emitters, and the EC.
Webinar: The role of Bioenergy with CCS to deliver negative emissions	18 December 2023	160	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborating with ETIP Bioenergy. Presenting the state-of-play of CCS in Europe and the role of carbon removal solutions.
CCSA/ZEP Webinar Launch: Charting the course for CCS	9 January 2024	250	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify key barriers and enablers and provide recommendations to European policymakers to support the deployment of the CO₂ shipping market. Present key findings of shipping report and facilitate a discussion.
ZEP Projects Network: Porthos	24-25 January 2024	170	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create a forum where CCS and CCU project developers exchange information, discuss enablers and hurdles, good practices, and de-risking planned and ongoing projects across Europe.

Meeting	Date	Attendees	Key ZEP contributions
Webinar: Scaling up storage: mapping Europe's CO ₂ storage sites	24 May 2024	350	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate discussions between the Commission and experts on ensuring accurate communication about CO₂ storage capacity estimates and the status of ongoing and planned storage projects. Provide experts and the Commission the opportunity to discuss the needs of the CO₂ storage atlas ahead of its formation.
Webinar: Fostering public support for CCS: behind the scenes of stakeholder management	20 June 2024	100	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate knowledge sharing and lessons learned about stakeholder management—both successes and failures—that have shaped the trajectory of CCS projects.
Webinar: Certifying high-quality permanent carbon removals	7 October 2024	129	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highlight a series of recommendations to inform the work of the European Commission in developing certification methodologies for permanent CDR. Enable a nuanced discussion to inform policymakers of the consensus in the industrial carbon management community.
ZEP-ING Workshop: “Financing CCS- Making Projects Bankable”	27 November 2024	32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support ICM stakeholders in understanding the different types of financing for CCS projects. Zoom-in on private project financing.
Workshop “CO ₂ Storage monitoring: Technologies and Lessons Learned”	31 January 2025	117	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide insights into the development, permitting and monitoring of commercial, operating CO₂ storage sites Outline the key components and design of monitoring plans Share knowledge and experiences with European competent authorities Connect independent observers and regulators with counterparts globally
ZEP-EBN Workshop “De-risking CCS Projects: The Role of Insurance”	10 April 2025	122	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help project developers, transport and storage operators, policymakers, investors, and other stakeholders in the industrial carbon management community gain insights from world-leading experts about different pathways to insure and de-risk CCS projects in Europe.

Meeting	Date	Attendees	Key ZEP contributions
ZEP Projects Network: Ravenna CCS	24-25 June 2025	172	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Create a forum where CCS and CCU project developers exchange information, discuss enablers and hurdles, good practices, and de-risking planned and ongoing projects across Europe.